

MEDICINAL GAZANDAOT (URTICA DIOCA L.) SEED PRODUCTION AND CULTIVATION AGROTECHNICS OF THE PLANT AND ITS USE IN MEDICINE

¹Rasulov Ilham Makhmudovich, ²Umurov Jamal Yashinovich

^{1,2}Research Institute of Plant Genetic Resources

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7643902>

Abstract. Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 10, 2020 No. 4670 “on measures for the protection, cultural cultivation, processing and rational use of available resources of wild growing medicinal plants”, decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 20, 2022 No. 139 PF “on measures to effectively use the raw material base of medicinal plants, to create, According to the work plan approved in 2023 at the Research Institute of Plant Genetic Resources, it was planned to enrich the insitiut gene pool, plant in a large experimental area to provide seeds of the National genbankka medicinal gazanaoft plant.

Keywords: Gazandaoat, extract, mesophyte, kamed, protoporphyrin, coproporphyrin, cytosterin, urticin glycoside, iron, phytoncides, quercetin, coffee, coumaric, ferula, Ant, pantothene.

OGRITI, employees of the Department of selection, seed production and agrotechnics of medicinal plants together using the experiments of scientists, literature, medicinal gazandaot (Urtica dioica L.,) when we study the plant, this medicinal plant (Urticaceae) belongs to the family and is a mesophyte plant with typical gray soils, suitable for flat land areas, conditionally irrigated. Pop, Kosonsoy of Namangan region, Formish, Velvet, Zamin of Jizzakh region, Bostanlyq, Melonaron, Parkent of Tashkent region, Kuva, Rishton districts of Fergana region and all over Uzbekistan, in shady wet areas, is a perennial plant growing on the slopes of ditches and consists of creeping, branched rhizome. The STEM is erect, four-sided, non-branched, 60-170 cm high, covered with long scaly, stinging and short simple hairs. The leaves are ovoid-lanceolate, large-toothed along the edges, 8-17 cm long and 2-8 cm wide. The flowers are unisexual, small, have a simple inflorescence divided into four, collected in spiky cobs between the branches that come out of the leaf axils. The fruits consist of an ovoid or elliptical yellowish-gray nutty appearance.

Gazandaoth (Urtica dioica L.,) grows in early spring and forms large leaves within 15-20 days after the snow melts, at this time the content of vitamins is high.

It grows very quickly, the moment of flowering begins mainly in early June. Gazandoat retains its green leaves even after fruiting. Blooms from June to September, produces fruits from July. In medicine, plant leaves are used, from which liquid extract, tinctures and nastoykas are made.

Medicinal gazanda (Urtica dioica L.,) collection of plant raw materials and its quality. The collection of medicinal gazandao'ti leaves can be carried out almost everywhere, only raw materials are not collected near roads with intensive Motor Transport. The collection of raw materials is carried out by hand, for which leather or tarpaulin gloves are worn. Gazandeaare collected by plucking the leaves from the stems and branches. Gazandaoth is not grown for medical purposes, but is grown near poultry farms and enterprises that receive chlorophyll from

gazandaot. Since gazandaot is a root bachkili plant, the rhizome is grown cut into cuts. To do this, the plant is dug up in early spring, the rhizomes are cut into cuts.

Medicinal gazanda (Urtica dioica L.) the grass is planted in rows, 5 root bacilli are planted per 1 m. Row spacing should be up to 50 cm. Gazanoat grows rapidly. For medicinal purposes, the leaves of the plant during the flowering period are used. The leaves should be immediately spread out for drying. It is dried in the shade, in rooms with good air circulation, on shelves or in dryers. The leaves are spread in one layer before drying. The finished raw material consists of green leaves that have not lost their color, and the moisture content in it should not exceed 14%. The raw material should not contain residues of stems, inflorescences, it is necessary to remove callous or darkened leaves. The gazandeoft Leaf is stored in boxes or containers, it breaks easily in very thin and soft containers.

Medicinal gazandaot (Urtica dioica L.) the plant is used in medicine as a blood deterrent and as a means to increase the contraction activity of the uterus and increase blood clotting. They are very effective in climacteric, bavonsil and other bleeding. Its leaves are used to treat anemia. Medicinal gazandeof herbal teas are also included in the composition. The fruit of the Gazanda plant was used by Abu Ali ibn Sina for the treatment of shortness of breath, using its Leaf as a blood flow deterrent and an surgic agent. A decoction, decoction and leaf powder made from the leaves of the plant are used in folk medicine to treat chest pain, shortness of breath, diabetes, fever and bod diseases. In addition to these, a decoction and poroshogi made from the leaf of the sputum transporter in respiratory diseases, the diuretic (in diseases of the urinary tract and kidneys-stones) is also used as a medicine that stops blood flow in Gazando prepare a decoction from the plant, put a glass of boiling water in a container with a lid, put a tablespoon Then strain in gauze. The tincture is drunk one tablespoon half an hour before meals 3-4 times a day. In scientific medicine, medicinal preparations of the gazanda plant (tincture, liquid extract) are used as a stopping drug for blood leaks (from the lungs, neck, intestines, hemorrhoids, menstrual irregularities, uterine bleeding), as well as for the treatment of chronic wounds, diseases caused by a lack of vitamins (avitaminoses). The leaf of the Gazanda plant is included in the composition of tea collections, which are used for gastric diseases and as a blood stop drug. Chlorophyll extracted from its Leaf is used as a dye substance in the food industry and in pharmaceuticals. Gazandeot leaves contain up to 269 mg% of vitamin C, carotene and other carotenoids (up to 50 mg%), vitamins of Group B and K, Ant, pantothene and other organic acids. The leaves contain up to 5% chlorophyll, more than 2% tannins, kamed, protoporphyrin, coproporphyrin, cytosterin, urticin glycoside, iron, phytoncides, quercetin, coffee, coumaric, ferulic acids, acetylcholine, histamine and 5-hydroxytryptamine.

REFERENCES

1. Resolution of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 10, 2020 No. 4670 PP-4670 “on measures for the protection, cultural cultivation, processing and rational use of available resources of wild hoda growing medicinal plants”.
2. Decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 20, 2022 PF-139 ”on measures to effectively use the raw material base of medicinal plants, create a chain of added value by supporting processing
3. H.X., Kharlamov I.A. Home use of healing plants. - Tashkent, Uzssr publishing house” Medicine”, 1985.-21 P.

4. Kholmatov X.X., Qasimov A.I. Dictionary of Russian-Latin-Uzbek medicinal plants. - Tashkent, publishing house named after Ibn Sina, 1992. - 200 b.
5. Kholmatov X.X., Qasimov A.I., Medicinal plants. - Tashkent, Publishing and Printing Association named after Ibn Sina, 1994. - 368 b.
6. Kholmatov H.X., Akhmedov U.A. Pharmacognosy: textbook for students of medical universities. - Tashkent: Publishing and Printing Association named after Ibn Sina, 1995. - 623 b.